

Cognitive Dissonance in Online Shopping Experiences and Impulsive Buying Among E-Commerce Users in Indonesia

Bayu Cunda Satria¹, Retno Tanding Suryandari²

^{1,2}Master of Management, Sebelas Maret University, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the influence of Online Customer Shopping Experience on Impulsive Buying and Cognitive Dissonance in the context of e-commerce use in Indonesia. Based on data from 420 respondents, it was found that the most widely used e-commerce platforms are Tokopedia, TikTok Shop, and Shopee. The majority of respondents purchase products such as clothing, accessories, as well as beauty and personal care products, which shows the dominance of lifestyle needs in online shopping behavior. The results of the analysis show that the online shopping experience has a significant effect on impulse purchases, which can then trigger post-purchase cognitive dissonance. In addition, it was found that Impulsive Buying also mediates the relationship between Online Customer Shopping Experience and Cognitive Dissonance. Thus, an engaging and emotional shopping experience not only encourages spontaneous purchases, but also contributes to dissatisfaction if the purchase results are not as expected. These findings provide important implications for e-commerce service providers to design shopping experiences that are not only visually appealing and promotional, but also able to meet consumer expectations to reduce the potential for cognitive dissonance.

KEYWORDS: Cognitive Dissonance, e-commerce, Customer Experience, Impulsive Buying, Online Customer Shopping Experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consumer purchasing behavior in Indonesia has undergone significant changes with the increasing ease of acquiring goods and services both offline and online (Junejo, 2023; Murdiana et al., 2024). The digital era has fueled the global popularity of online shopping (Dr. B. K. Singh, 2022; Virmani et al., 2023), with the number of e-commerce users in Indonesia reaching 178.94 million in 2022 and projected to rise to 244.67 million by 2027 (dataindonesia.id). The Financial Services Authority (OJK) reports that 88.1% of internet users in Indonesia have utilized e-commerce services (Mahmood, 2016), underscoring the centrality of e-commerce in consumer behavior. Post-pandemic, both millennials and older generations have demonstrated a consistent increase in online shopping due to the availability of essential goods online (Firmandani et al., 2021; Lestari, 2019; Murdiana et al., 2024; Suryadi et al., 2022; Wijaya et al., 2024).

The most frequently purchased items by Indonesian consumers include fashion (68%), gadgets (44%), electronics (35%), and other products such as food and cosmetics (We Are Social; Suryadi et al., 2022). Both online and offline shopping experiences influence consumer purchasing behavior, particularly impulsive buying, which occurs spontaneously without prior planning (Rook, 1987; Baumeister, 2002; Verplanken & Herabadi, 2001). Platforms such as Shopee, Tokopedia, Lazada, and TikTok Shop compete by innovating and introducing new features to enhance consumer experiences (Alam et al., 2020; Imtiaz Ali et al., 2018; Lim et al., 2016; Qin et al., 2020). Events such as “Harbolnas” (National Online Shopping Day) and “date-based” promotions (11.11, 12.12) have stimulated impulsive buying, with transactions reaching IDR 25.7 trillion in 2023 (idEA; kontan.id), and the FMCG sector is expected to grow by 13.9% during Harbolnas 2024 (Handriani et al., 2024; Putri, 2023; Saputra et al., 2024; Wilson & Christella, 2019).

Preferences for online shopping are driven by free shipping promotions (54.9%), coupons/discounts, customer testimonials (52%), ease of checkout (45%), store reputation (40.1%), return policies (28.8%), and cash-on-delivery options (28.1%) (We Are Social, 2023). Other contributing factors include time savings, price comparisons, discounts, and product variety (goodstats.com). However, risks such as fraud, product discrepancies, delivery delays, and data breaches—as seen in the Tokopedia and Bhinneka cases (2020)—erode consumer trust (Pavlou, 2003; Fauzi et al., 2024; Putra et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2020; Zhang & Yu, 2020). Such risks may trigger cognitive dissonance, defined as the psychological discomfort experienced after making a purchase (Festinger, 1957; Cooper & Carlsmith, 2001; Wahyuni et al., 2021).

Cognitive dissonance arises when purchases conflict with consumers' values or needs (Brehm, 1956; Singh, 2012; Akram et al., 2021; Yap & Gaur, 2014). A Slickdeals survey found that 74% of online shoppers in Indonesia regretted their purchases; the main reasons were goods not matching their price (39%), unused items (34%), and overspending (32%). Psychological factors such as perception, motivation, learning, beliefs, and attitudes play a dominant role in digital consumer behavior (Chowdhury, 2023; Handriani et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2019; Panjaitan et al., 2018; Solomon, 2013; Fernandez-Lores et al., 2024; Priya & Sharma, 2023; Abigail et al., 2024; Haqiqi, 2019).

E-commerce platforms provide information that shapes both rational and impulsive purchase decisions, yet such information is often excessive or misleading, leading to consumer confusion (Blagoeva et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2008; Kumar et al., 2017; Petcharat & Leelasantitham, 2021; Salam et al., 2003; He et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2006). Perceptions of information overload positively influence consumers' intention to repurchase online through impulsive buying and cognitive dissonance (Akram et al., 2021; C. Liao et al., 2017; Setyani et al., 2019).

Understanding these risks and adopting preventive measures—such as product research, scrutinizing seller reputation and reviews, choosing trustworthy platforms, and utilizing reliable customer service—can help consumers make more prudent purchase decisions and reduce the likelihood of cognitive dissonance in the future. This study aims to examine consumers' regret experiences resulting from impulsive purchases and their impact on future online shopping behavior.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer Experience (CX) and Online Customer's Shopping Experience (OCSE)

CX encompasses all customer interactions with the company before and after the purchase and involves the emotional aspects that affect satisfaction and loyalty (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016). The Schmitt model identifies five key dimensions of customer experience—sensory, emotional, cognitive, social, and functional—that companies can manage to create positive experiences (Schmitt, 1999). In online shopping, the convenience of 24-hour service, fast delivery, and complete product information have a positive impact on satisfaction (Perera & Sachitra, 2019), while site quality such as design, functionality, and usability are significant predictors of satisfaction (Deyalage & Kulathunga, 2019).

OCSE encompasses cognitive, emotional, and behavioral interactions when shopping digitally (Rose et al., 2012). Site design, ease of navigation, transaction security, and interactivity affect satisfaction and loyalty (McLean & Wilson, 2016). Positive OCSEs increase trust, purchases, and long-term relationships (Bleier et al., 2019). Important factors in CX–OCSE include intuitive interface design and UX (Hassanein & Head, 2007), trust and security of transactions (McCole, 2004), and personalization of product recommendations (Arora et al., 2008; Schiffman & Kanuk, 2008).

Impulsive Buying

Impulse purchases are influenced by internal factors such as personality and emotions as well as external factors such as promotion and product placement (Stern, 1962). Stern classifies four types: pure impulse (spontaneous), reminder impulse (remembering previous needs) (Hubert & Griffiths, 2018), suggestion impulse (due to product quality/benefits) (Nurlinda et al., 2020; Park et al., 2012), and planned impulse (a combination of plan and spontaneity) (Badgaiyan & Verma, 2015).

Pure Impulsive Buying

Impulse shopping is higher online than offline (Virmani et al., 2023; Fernando-Lores et al., 2024; Rundle-Thiele et al., 2013; Vicdan et al., 2007). Online consumers tend to be unplanned and find it difficult to control the buying impulse (Gong et al., 2020; Rook & Fisher, 1995; Savastano et al., 2024; Xiang et al., 2016; Singh et al., 2023) as well as having a strong emotional drive to buy (Ampadu et al., 2022; Koufaris et al., 2002; Parboteeah et al., 2009). Pure impulsive buying decisions are spontaneous without considering the consequences and are triggered by situational temptations that are difficult to control (Utama et al., 2021; Verplanken & Herabadi, 2001a; Hassan et al., 2016; Akram et al., 2018). This temptation can result in a strong emotional attachment to the product (Gulfraz et al., 2022; Park et al., 2012; Smoke, n.d.; Spiteri Cornish, 2020). Impulsive buying includes affective (pleasure, joy, guilt) and cognitive (absence of planning, elaborative thinking) aspects (Rook & Fisher, 1995; Dittmar, 2005; Beatty & Ferrell, 1998; Sharma et al., 2010; Sohn & Lee, 2017; Verplanken & Herabadi, 2001). Website design and layout factors can increase impulse purchase intent (Chen et al., 2017), as well as consumer trust in the platform (Gong et al., 2020). The analysis of Redine et al. (2023) identified five categories of online impulsive drivers: individual factors (Parboteeah et al., 2009; Khan et al., 2016), product factors, website factors (Vicdan et al., 2007), social factors, and situational factors. Attractive visual displays (Chen

& Yao, 2018) as well as credible positive reviews increase impulse purchases (Huang et al., 2023; Lina & Ahluwalia, 2021; Xu et al., 2020).

Cognitive Dissonance

Cognitive dissonance arises when behaviors or opinions are inconsistent and give rise to emotional discomfort (Hawkins & Mothersbaugh, 2016; Cooper & Carlsmith, 2015; Festinger, 1957; Morvan, 2017; Harmon-Jones & Mills, 2019). The greater the dissonance, the stronger the motivation to reduce it (Brehm, 1956; Harmon-Jones & Mills, 2019; Weingarten & Lagerkvist, 2023). Festinger (1957) stated that dissonance occurs due to inappropriate relationships between cognition, which is a motivating factor in itself. Individuals tend to justify decisions even if they differ from their beliefs (Tavris & Aronson, 2007; Aronson, 1999). These inconsistencies create psychological tension and encourage the search for consistency (Devine et al., 1999; Harmon-Jones, 2012; Steele, 1988). Indicators include emotional discomfort, changes in attitudes, behavioral rationalization, and information avoidance. In the context of purchase, dissonance occurs after purchase if the product does not meet expectations or is considered the wrong choice (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Li & Choudhury, 2021; Nam, 2023). Consumers then reevaluate or use strategies to reduce non-conformity (Festinger, 1957 in Barta et al., 2023; Chatterjee et al., 2023; Rees et al., 2015; Chung & Cheng, 2018; Draycott & Dabbs, 1998).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Research Concept Model

(Sources: Schmitt, 1999; Lemon & Verhoef, 2016; Hawkins–Stern, 1962; Festinger, 1957).

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative approach with descriptive and explanatory designs to test the hypotheses developed by the researcher. The research design serves as a blueprint for data collection, measurement, and analysis (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The quantitative approach was chosen because it aims to test theories with statistical procedures (Kusumastuti, 2020).

The variables tested included Online Customer Shopping Experience (OCSE) as an independent variable (X), Impulsive Buying (IB) as a mediating variable (M), and Cognitive Dissonance (CD) as a dependent variable (Y). OCSE indicators refer to sensory, emotional, cognitive, social, functional experiences (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016; Schmitt, 1999) as well as online shopping experiences, including interface design, trust, security, and personalization (Bleier et al., 2019; Pandey & Chawla, 2018; Hassanein & Head, 2007; McCole, 2004; Arora et al., 2008; Schiffman, 2008). IB is measured based on aspects of spontaneous buying, less attention to consequences, and triggered by situational factors (Verplanken & Herabadi, 2009; Hassan & Shiu, 2016; Khan & Dhar, 2006). CD is measured through emotional discomfort, attitudinal changes, behavioral rationalization, and information avoidance (Festinger, 1957; 1962).

The study population was e-commerce users who had made impulse purchases. The sampling technique used is convenience sampling because the population is not known for sure (Etikan et al., 2016). Based on the basic rules of the Partial Least Squares (PLS) method, the minimum number of samples is determined to be 5–10 times the number of indicators (Hair et al., 2011; Kock & Hadaya, 2018). With 42 indicators, the number of samples was set at 420 respondents. Respondents were selected based on the following criteria: (1) active e-commerce users over the age of 16 and (2) having made impulse purchases in the last six months.

Data was collected through an online survey using a Google Form questionnaire after respondents expressed their willingness to participate. This study uses primary data from questionnaires and secondary data from documents or literature studies. Variables are measured on a Likert scale of 1–5 (strongly disagree – strongly agree).

Data analysis uses Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) because of its ability to handle complex models with relatively small samples (Hair Jr et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2016). The analysis included a descriptive test to describe the characteristics of the data, a validity test (Ghozali, 2009) using factor analysis and AVE (>0.5), a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (>0.7) (Priyatno, 2018; Suharsaputra, 2014; Hair Jr et al., 2014), as well as hypothesis testing and mediation through bootstrapping methods to determine the significance of direct and indirect influences (Zhao et al., 2010; Hair et al., 2017).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

This study involved 420 respondents using e-commerce in Indonesia. The results showed a significant correlation between impulsive buying 4946behaviour and the appearance of regret and dissatisfaction after a purchase. Around 71% of respondents (300 people) admitted to making impulse purchases often or occasionally, with the main triggers being discounts/promos (187 respondents), followed by attractive advertisements (58) and product availability (37). After impulse purchases, 54% of respondents (225) stated often/sometimes regretted; 51% (216) admit their purchases are influenced by negative emotions such as stress or dissatisfaction. Dissatisfaction with the product is quite dominant (190 sometimes dissatisfied; 72 often dissatisfied), mainly due to inappropriate quality (131) and price considered too high (101); Major/moderate regret was reported by 68% of respondents (286).

In terms of demographics, the majority of respondents were male (59.5%; 249 people) and were in the age range of 22–27 years (51.9%; 218 people). The geographical distribution is quite wide: the most from Bandung (111), Jakarta (76), and other categories (212), strengthening the validity of the data (Raharjo, 2020).

Product preferences showed the dominance of clothing and accessories (331 respondents), followed by beauty/personal care products (189), electronics (122), and home appliances (113). These findings show that Indonesian consumers not only use e-commerce for basic needs, but also to support lifestyle and personal comfort; The purchase of electronic and household products indicates trust in online platforms in providing high-value goods.

Outer Model Analysis Validity Test

The high outer loading indicates a lot of similarities in the construct. The minimum value of outer loading is 0.7 (Hair et al., 2022). The following are the results of the outer loading test which can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Outer Loading

	<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>
CD-1	0.791			
CD-12	0.802			
CD-13	0.831			
CD-14	0.807			
CD-15	0.787			
CD-16	0.808			
CD-2	0.795			
CD-3	0.805			
CD-4	0.806			
CD-6	0.804			
CD-7	0.818			
CD-8	0.82			
CD-9	0.811			

	<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>
IB-1		0.783		
IB-2		0.783		
IB-3		0.784		
IB-4		0.792		
IB-6		0.786		
IB-7		0.767		
IB-8		0.767		
OCSE-1			0.818	
OCSE-10			0.783	
OCSE-12			0.785	
OCSE-13			0.8	
OCSE-14			0.789	
OCSE-15			0.801	
OCSE-16			0.803	
OCSE-17			0.778	
OCSE-18			0.797	
OCSE-2			0.78	
OCSE-3			0.802	
OCSE-5			0.803	
OCSE-7			0.82	
OCSE-8			0.833	
OCSE-9			0.788	
<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>				1

Convergent validity refers to the extent to which a construct is able to measure each of its indicators. Convergent validity testing can be performed by evaluating *the Average Variance Extracted (AVE)*. According to Hair et al. (2022), when the AVE value is greater than 0.5, the construct is able to explain more than 50% of the indicator’s variations.

Table 2. AVE

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Average variance extracted (AVE)</i>
<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	0.65
<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	0.609
<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	0.638

All constructs in this model have qualified convergent validity with AVE values above 0.5. *Cognitive Dissonance* has an AVE of 0.65, *Impulsive Buying* of 0.609, and an *Online Customer Shopping Experience* of 0.638. This shows that each construct is able to explain more than 50% of the variance of the indicators used to measure it.

The next criterion that needs to be considered is *the value of cross loading*. According to this criterion, *the outer loading* of an indicator on the related construct must be greater than the *cross loading* on the other construct. The value of *the loading factor* can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Cross Loading

	<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>
CD-1	0.791	0.514	0.377	-0.171
CD-12	0.802	0.523	0.431	-0.177
CD-13	0.831	0.528	0.404	-0.169
CD-14	0.807	0.512	0.407	-0.153
CD-15	0.787	0.515	0.432	-0.17
CD-16	0.808	0.476	0.417	-0.108
CD-2	0.795	0.485	0.411	-0.19
CD-3	0.805	0.497	0.391	-0.143
CD-4	0.806	0.491	0.388	-0.123
CD-6	0.804	0.514	0.42	-0.152
CD-7	0.818	0.491	0.447	-0.144
CD-8	0.82	0.518	0.411	-0.179
CD-9	0.811	0.503	0.453	-0.17
IB-1	0.443	0.783	0.491	-0.354
IB-2	0.484	0.783	0.473	-0.355
IB-3	0.479	0.784	0.494	-0.378
IB-4	0.53	0.792	0.537	-0.379
IB-6	0.509	0.786	0.532	-0.359
IB-7	0.498	0.767	0.489	-0.41
IB-8	0.473	0.767	0.488	-0.336
OCSE-1	0.446	0.498	0.818	-0.475
OCSE-10	0.368	0.54	0.783	-0.507
OCSE-12	0.389	0.504	0.785	-0.471
OCSE-13	0.386	0.555	0.8	-0.475
OCSE-14	0.451	0.531	0.789	-0.484
OCSE-15	0.376	0.519	0.801	-0.467
OCSE-16	0.373	0.507	0.803	-0.484
OCSE-17	0.387	0.526	0.778	-0.484
OCSE-18	0.44	0.502	0.797	-0.446
OCSE-2	0.408	0.487	0.78	-0.494
OCSE-3	0.419	0.536	0.802	-0.473

	<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>
OCSE-5	0.414	0.495	0.803	-0.488
OCSE-7	0.444	0.506	0.82	-0.46
OCSE-8	0.449	0.511	0.833	-0.465
OCSE-9	0.405	0.483	0.788	-0.462
Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience	-0.196	-0.471	-0.595	1

Based on Table 3, it can be stated that the value of each of the *outer loading* is higher than the cross loading in the other constructs. Another important criterion to consider in *discriminant validity* is the *heterotrait monotrait ratio* (HTMT). HTMT is the *mean* of the entire relationship between the cross-construct indicators. According to (Hair et al., 2022), the maximum value of HTMT correlation is 0.9. HTMT correlation values of more than 0.9 indicate a lack of *discriminant validity*.

Table 4. Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>
<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>				
<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	0.677			
<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	0.536	0.693		
<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	0.2	0.498	0.608	

Based on Table 4, there is no HTMT correlation value greater than 0.9. The value has met the HTMT criteria and has met the *discriminant validity test*.

Reliability Test

The next test that needs to be done on the outer model is the *internal consistency reliability test*. This test was carried out through *Cronbach alpha* and *composite reliability values*. The *Cronbach alpha value* describes the *Cronbach correlation* in a construct, while the *composite reliability* looks at the difference in the *outer loading* of the *Cronbach Alpha*. Hair et al. (2022) stated that the *Cronbach alpha* and *composite reliability* values received must be more than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2022).

Table 5. Composite Reliability

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	<i>Composite reliability (rho_a)</i>	<i>Composite reliability (rho_c)</i>	<i>Average variance extracted (AVE)</i>
<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	0.955	0.955	0.96	0.65
<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	0.893	0.894	0.916	0.609
<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	0.959	0.96	0.964	0.638

The test results in table 5 show that all latent variables meet the reliability test criteria. This is based on the *Cronbach alpha* value and *composite reliability* of all latent variables with values above 0.7. Therefore, all latent variables are declared reliable after meeting all measurement criteria.

Inner Model Analysis

The next evaluation that is carried out when the model measurement is declared valid and reliable is the *Structural Model Assessment* or commonly called the *internal model evaluation*. According to (Hair et al., 2022), the evaluation of the inner model is carried out with several tests, such as collinearity, significance and relevance of model relationships, *Model's Explanatory Power*, and *Model's Predictive Power* which will be discussed below.

Test R Square (R²)

Table 6 shows the results of the test analysis of the R-Square value.

Table 6. R-Square Test (R²)

	<i>R-square</i>	<i>R-square adjusted</i>
<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	0.452	0.449
<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	0.413	0.412

The R Square value for *Cognitive Dissonance* of 0.452 indicates that 45.2% variability in cognitive dissonance can be explained by *Impulsive Buying*, *Online Customer Shopping Experience*, and their interactions. While the R Square value for *Impulsive Buying* of 0.413 indicates that 41.3% of the variability in impulsive behaviour is explained by the online shopping experience. The Adjusted R Square, which is not much different, indicates that this model is stable and quite powerful.

Assess the structural model for collinearity issues (VIF)

Collinearity is a condition in which two or more (independent) predictor variables in a model have a high linear relationship, meaning they are highly correlated with each other. The collinearity test can be done by looking at the VIF value. If the value is VIF < 5, then the model is fit and can be continued in the next analysis. The results of the VIF value test can be seen in Table 7 below.

Table 7. Cholinity Test

	VIVID
<i>Impulsive Buying -> Cognitive Dissonance</i>	1.74
<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Cognitive Dissonance</i>	2.098
<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Impulsive Buying</i>	1
<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Cognitive Dissonance</i>	1.582

It can be seen in Table 7 above that the VIF value between the research variables has met the test limit, which is < 5. From the *internal model testing*, it was found that the model in general is quite good.

Path Analysis

At this stage, the test is carried out by looking at the *path coefficient* value and the t-value. A *path coefficient* value close to 1 indicates a positive relationship and conversely, a value close to 0 indicates a weak relationship in the model structure. Furthermore, the value t indicates the significance of a relationship between variables at a given error level. In this study, the researcher used a significance level *error* of 5% which means that the t-value must be greater than 1.96. The following are the *path coefficient* and *t values* shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Path Coefficient Value

	Original Sample Estimate	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics	P-Values
Impulsive Buying -> Cognitive Dissonance	0.542	0.048	11.373	0.000
Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Cognitive Dissonance	0.312	0.06	5.175	0.000
Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Impulsive Buying	0.643	0.037	17.144	0.000
Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Cognitive Dissonance	0.187	0.044	4.228	0.000

Impulsive Buying had a significant effect on Cognitive Dissonance with a coefficient of 0.542, a T-value of 11.373, and a p-value of 0.000, which suggests that impulsive buying 4951behaviour can increase the cognitive dissonance felt by consumers after shopping. Online Customer Shopping Experience also has a direct effect on Cognitive Dissonance with a coefficient of 0.312, a T-value of 5.175, and a p-value of 0.000. In addition, Online Customer Shopping Experience also has a significant influence on Impulsive Buying with a coefficient of 0.643, a T-value of 17.144, and a p-value of 0.000, which indicates that the online shopping experience felt by consumers encourages impulse purchases. The interaction between Impulsive Buying and Online Customer Shopping Experience as a moderation construct also had a significant effect on Cognitive Dissonance (coefficient 0.187, T = 4.228, p = 0.000), which showed the presence of a moderation effect in the relationship. Furthermore, it is the path coefficient and t value values with indirect influence shown in the following Table 9.

Table 9. Indirect Effect

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T (O/STDEV)	statistics	P values
Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Impulsive Buying -> Cognitive Dissonance	0.348	0.349	0.036	9.752		0.000

Online Customer Shopping Experience also has an indirect influence on Cognitive Dissonance through Impulsive Buying with a coefficient of 0.348, a T value of 9.752, and a p-value of 0.000. This means that most of the influence of the online shopping experience on cognitive dissonance occurs indirectly through impulse buying 4951behaviour.

Mediation Test

Table 10. Mediation Test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T (O/STDEV)	statistics	P values
Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Impulsive Buying -> Cognitive Dissonance	0.348	0.349	0.036	9.752		0.000

Online Customer Shopping Experience also has an indirect influence on *Cognitive Dissonance* through *Impulsive Buying* with a coefficient of 0.348, a T value of 9.752, and a p-value of 0.000. This means that most of the influence of the online shopping experience on cognitive dissonance occurs indirectly through impulse buying behaviour.

Moderation Test

Table 11. Moderation Test

	<i>Original Sample Estimate</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T-Statistics</i>	<i>P-Values</i>
<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience -> Cognitive Dissonance</i>	0.187	0.044	4.228	0.000

The interaction between *Impulsive Buying* and *Online Customer Shopping Experience* had an effect on *Cognitive Dissonance*, with a coefficient of 0.187, a T-value of 4.228, and a p-value of 0.000. Since the p-value < 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted. This suggests that *Online Customer Shopping Experience* moderates the relationship between *Impulsive Buying* and *Cognitive Dissonance*. In other words, the influence of impulse purchases on cognitive dissonance will become stronger when the online shopping experience that consumers feel is more intense or significant.

Effect Size Value

Next, the test that needs to be done at the stage of *Assess the model's explanatory power* is to look at the *effect size* value or *f²*. The effect size evaluation was carried out by looking at the *f²* value to determine the magnitude of the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables in a model. The guideline for assessing *f²* is that values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, respectively, represent small, medium, and large influences (Hair *et al.*, 2022). The following is the *f-square* value of each construct which can be seen in Table 12.

Table 12. Effect Size Value

	<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i>	<i>Impulsive Buying</i>
<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	0.308	
<i>Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	0.085	0.705
<i>Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience</i>	0.069	

Impulsive Buying had a moderate effect on *Cognitive Dissonance* ($f^2 = 0.308$), while *Online Customer Shopping Experience* had a large effect on *Impulsive Buying* ($f^2 = 0.705$) and a small effect on *Cognitive Dissonance* ($f^2 = 0.085$). Moderation of *Impulsive Buying x Online Customer Shopping Experience* interactions had a small effect on *Cognitive Dissonance* ($f^2 = 0.069$).

Discussion

1. The Effect of Impulsive Buying on Cognitive Dissonance

The results showed that impulse buying had a positive and significant effect on cognitive dissonance ($\beta = 0.542$; $T = 11.373$; $p < 0.001$). These findings are in line with Festinger's theory of cognitive dissonance which explains the emergence of psychological discomfort when behavior does not match values or expectations. Consumers who buy goods spontaneously tend to experience regret, confusion, or post-purchase dissatisfaction. Previous studies have also supported these results (Wanninayake, 2012; George *et al.*, 2010; Kocamaz, 2020).

2. The Effect of Online Shopping Experience on Cognitive Dissonance
Online shopping experience had a significant effect on cognitive dissonance ($\beta = 0.312$; $T = 5.175$; $p < 0.001$). The more complex or frustrating the shopping experience is (e.g., product display differences, complicated checkout processes, or delivery delays), the greater the potential for dissonance (Anas et al., 2023; Kudo et al., 2018). On the contrary, positive and consistent experiences lower the risk.
3. The Influence of Online Shopping Experience on Impulse Purchases
The analysis showed that the experience of online shopping had a positive effect on impulse purchases ($\beta = 0.643$; $T = 17.144$; $p < 0.001$). Features such as limited-time promotions, personalized product recommendations, ease of checkout, and attractive interfaces encourage unplanned purchase decisions (Anas et al., 2023).
4. The Role of Impulse Purchase Moderation
Impulse purchases moderated the association between online shopping experience and cognitive dissonance ($\beta = 0.187$; $T = 4.228$; $p < 0.001$). The more engaging the digital shopping experience, the stronger the negative effect of impulse purchases on cognitive dissonance (Chetioui, 2023; Chen & Ku, 2021).
5. The Role of Impulse Buying Mediation
It was also found that the mediating effect of impulse purchases on the relationship between online shopping experience and cognitive dissonance ($\beta = 0.348$; $T = 9.752$; $p < 0.001$). A pleasant online shopping experience not only encourages impulse purchases, but also indirectly increases cognitive dissonance (Meena, 2023; Anas et al., 2023).

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study confirms that Online Customer Shopping Experience has a significant effect on Impulsive Buying and Cognitive Dissonance in e-commerce consumers in Indonesia. The results of the analysis show that attractive, interactive, and easily accessible shopping experiences on platforms such as Tokopedia, Shopee, and TikTok Shop encourage consumers to make impulse purchases, especially in lifestyle product categories such as clothing, accessories, and beauty products. Furthermore, impulse purchases have been shown to have a positive effect on the onset of cognitive dissonance, where consumers experience doubt, dissatisfaction, or regret after the transaction.

These findings also show that there is a direct influence of the online shopping experience on cognitive dissonance, both through the quality of services and products that do not meet expectations and through the emotional nature of the shopping experience that reinforces impulsive tendencies. The mediation analysis confirms that Impulsive Buying is an important mechanism that bridges the relationship between Online Customer Shopping Experience and Cognitive Dissonance.

Overall, this study expands our understanding of the behavioral dynamics of digital consumers by showing that the online shopping experience not only influences purchasing decisions directly, but also impacts post-purchase psychological states. The practical implication is that e-commerce service providers need to design shopping experiences that are ethical, informative, and long-term satisfaction-oriented to minimize the risk of cognitive dissonance and increase consumer loyalty.

This study uses perceptual data so that it has not captured the actual behavior of consumers as a whole. Future research can integrate actual behavioral data (e.g., transaction history, frequency of visits, and patterns of digital interactions) with consumer perceptions to provide a more comprehensive picture. In addition, subsequent studies may examine the role of platform-specific features (e.g. recommendation systems, live shopping, or loyalty programs) in moderating the relationship between online shopping experiences and impulse purchases.

From an emotional perspective, qualitative research such as in-depth interviews or FGDs can identify specific emotions that arise when consumers experience cognitive dissonance (e.g., regret, frustration, guilt, or shame) and consumers' personal strategies for coping with them. This approach will provide a deeper understanding of the psychological dimensions of online shopping behavior and its implications for more ethical user experience design.

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